

Treating Eating and Drinking Disorders with Solution-Focused Therapy

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Eating and drinking disorder is a series of psychiatric disorders of having unhealthy eating and drinking habits. It begins with the obsession of the body shape, weight and the control of these two. It is seen in both men and women, however it is seen moreover in women. (Yıldız, 2019). It is more frequently seen in people whose socio-economic status is high. The person with the eating disorder is inclined to insufficient or excessive eating because of some kind of emotional and mental sources of a disorder. In severe cases, very serious health problems may take place and if it can not be cured, it can even be resulted in death. Eating disorders can manifest themselves with some symptoms such as; the person's excessive eating, or excessive restriction from foods, vomiting after eating, excessive exercising. The person pays a great deal of attention for his thinness and the shape of her body. She may be frightened to get fat.

Key words: Eating disorder, Anorexia nervosa Bulimia nervosa, Solution-based therapy, Realistic goals.

Introduction

Eating and drinking disorders are psychological situations that both have emotional and physical symptoms. They are cognitive disorders that shape, weight and the control of these are overvalued. Patients that have eating disorders usually judge themselves over their skills of controlling their kilos. American Psychiatric Association DSM-IV sorts anorexia nervosa,

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bulimia nervosa and another group that can't otherwise be specified. DSM-IV defined the diagnostic criteria for the first two groups, and some serious criteria that don't fit in these first two groups are considered in the third group. Eating disorders are generally treated by the cognitive therapies, however recently it is acknowledged that, to go deeper to the source of the problems takes a lot of time, causes time loss, and as the problem is dug, some other problems may come out. Patients and therapists may sometimes prefer to solve the problem quickly by focusing on the positive features of the patient. Solution-focused therapies are found by Steve De Shazer and Insoo Kim Berg. (Güner, 2021) According to this type of therapy, the therapist tries to detect in detail the future that the client desires, He also tries to unveil the client's strong sides and inner sources in order to reach his desired future. Solution-focused therapy can't be used for serious cases such as bipolar and schizophrenia. However it can be used to establish proper eating habits.

Literature Review

The American Psychiatric Association is the union that spearheaded the classification of eating disorders. DSM-IV sorts the disorders as; anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa and not otherwise specified disorders. (NOS). There are some criteria about anorexia nervosa and bulimia nervosa, however the serious disorders that don't meet the diagnostic criterion of these two are hold on for the third group that is called NOS. (not otherwise specified).

Because eating disorders share base psychopathologies, they are considered as cognitive disorders. These psychopathologies are; overvaluation of the shape, weight and control of these two. People who have eating disorders judge themselves and their eigenvalue over not only the weight and the shape of themselves but also over the skills of controlling their weight and shape. This psychopathology is typical of eating disorders and it's the same with women and men, and adolescents and adults. The majority of the patients who have this psychopathology are over involved with their weights and preoccupied with the slightest changes in their weights. (Todd, 2019). On the other hand they may be evading to know how much they weigh. These psychopathologies cause some effects on these patients; it may be hard for them to

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socialize or they may completely evade socialization. It may be hard to take off their clothes in front of other people and most of them don't like to be touched. (Fairburn, 2021)

Some patients exercise excessively, they may go to the gym many times a day. They may exaggerate the number of push-ups and sit-ups. They may even go on exercising even if they are injured. There may be many different motives behind these excessive exercising. Most of the time it means controlling weight or some kind of changing shape. In some situations it may also be used as mood regulation.

The most striking thing about anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa and NOS is; in which ways they resemble, more than in which ways they separate:

Anorexia nervosa

In order to diagnose anorexia nervosa, three features are required:

1. To be preoccupied with the shape, weight and the control of these and, evaluate oneself with these and the skill of controlling these.
2. Trying to protect a low weight actively even if he or she is already much below the expected weight.
3. Cessation of menstruation after adolescence in women. However this criterion

is being questioned and it may probably be removed from DSM-1V, because if the first two criteria is valid for the women, then their menstruation already ceases spontaneously. (Fairburn, 2021)

Anorexia nervosa patients are usually very thin and faint. They count calories, try to reduce the amount of what they eat. They have strict rules of eating. They avoid eating outside because they are obsessive about the ingredients of their meal. They want to be sure about what is inside their meal. They restrict their eating both in amount and in diversity. They have quite specific

dietary goals. They often go to scale and weigh themselves. They see themselves very fat when they look in the mirror, despite their thinness. Anorexia nervosa generally begins in the middle of adolescence with nutritional restriction.

<https://psikiyatri.org.tr/halka-yonelik/32/yeme-bozukluklari#:~:text=Yeme%20Bozukluklar%C4%B1%20anorek>

Bulimia nervosa

In order to diagnose bulimia nervosa three features are required, as well.

1. Overvalue shape, weight and control as in the anorexia nervosa.
2. Lose control and overeat as tucking-in, doing this recurrently.
3. Over Controlling of eating behavior, recurrent dietary restriction, sometimes making oneself vomit and using laxatives and diuretics. (This criterion separates the diagnosis of the anorexia nervosa and the bulimia nervosa). (Fairburn, 2021)

These patients evade eating with other people because they are anxious about what people will think about their eating too much. Sometimes patients feel the need of excretory after the excessive eating episodes. These patients may probably be

overweight or obese. Both of the groups of the patients may have depression, anxiety

disorder, substance use or self-harming behavior. Bulimia nervosa generally begins a little bit later than adolescence, sometimes at the end of the adolescence, sometimes in the early adulthood. (Pollen, 2019). Binge eating disorder patients are usually middle aged, one third of them are men, Their period of binge-eating may be discontinuous. (Fairburn, 2021)

NOS :The third group of the serious eating disorders that don't meet the criteria of the first two groups. (Not otherwise specified disorders).

This group involves the critical serious criteria that is different from the anorexia nervosa and the bulimia nervosa. For example there are patients who don't binge eat, however they have

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excretory disorder. There are many other categories of eating disorders such as; night eating syndrome. It is usually seen together with a sleeping disorder.

General mood of the patients with eating disorder:

They usually have negative thinking habits and may feel desperate. They may have recurrent thoughts about death and may have suicide thoughts and plans. They may have guilt feelings about so many subjects. Their social life is reduced. They quit joining some of the activities. They usually delay life and everything. Their skills of motivating themselves to do anything decreases. They may neglect their physical appearance and hygiene, they may neglect daily activities. They may feel depressed and unhappy. All these hard conditions require urgent solutions and in these situations it may be much more helpful to focus on the solutions rather than scrutinizing the whole life story of the person.

Solution-focused Therapy

Approximately 50 years ago Steve De Shazer and Insoo Kim Berg (Güner, 2021) developed goal-directed therapy focusing on the solutions rather than the problems. This therapeutic approach helps the patients to construct solutions by focusing on positive emotions and achieving the desired behavioral change by developing

satisfying solutions. Solution-focused therapy differs from the conventional therapies by focusing only on the practical sides of the conventional therapies but taking action rapidly and reaching the best solutions. In this kind of therapy there is no need for past stories, solution trials that don't work and complaints. Inner strength of the patient, his environmental sources and the future goals are the guiding elements that are required. This therapy focuses on the solution rather than the problem and in the therapy world this was so new.

For years it was focused on failing, imperfect and problematic parts of the patients. In this therapy however, it is aimed to focus on the powerful parts and the good sides of the patients. In this way it was thought to make them happier persons who enjoy life more. It is thought that in this way their mental health would be protected better. This was Martin Seligman's

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(Seligman, 1996) positive psychology principles that are emphasized in this kind of therapy. This therapy focuses on increasing the life quality of the person. It works on satisfaction, emotional pleasure, optimism, hopes and beliefs for the future. Positive attitudes personally redound, capacity to love, courage, forgiveness, wisdom and perseverance. They redound groups taking responsibility, thinking and caring of others, tolerating and morals. It is noticed that solutions might

be achieved by only focusing on the solutions without focusing on the problems, in shorter periods, furthermore by working in pleasure and joyfully.

The solution-focused therapist doesn't believe that it is required to know the reason for the problem in order to solve the problem. His aim is to cooperate with the patient about the solutions and the realistic goals. The client defines the goal he wants to achieve but he shows little interest about the past, reasons and the diagnosis.

Solution-focused therapy's formulations are quite clear, understandable and can be learned easily. Besides, it is a technique that brings quick results. In a research, 85 % of the clients reported that their purposes to come, have been met approximately in 6 or 8 sessions. Sometimes the results may be taken even earlier in 4 or 5 sessions.

The solution-focused therapist first detects and determines the strengths and the powerful inner sources of the client. He knows that a person is greater than his problems. What solves the problem is already potential in the client as his strong and useful features. It is meaningless to ignore these strengths and focus on the problem. It only causes the client to waste time. On the other hand, focusing on the powerful sources shortens the therapy journey.

Besides, talking about his powerful sides makes the therapy progress in a positive mood for the client. It also increases his motivation to attend the sessions.

Solution-focused therapies never use the techniques that have been already used and tried, they investigate the new techniques, find and use the ones that work. (Yağcı, 2020).

This kind of therapy assumes that the client can only know his goals and the way to where he wants to steer. The therapist asks his client which way he wanted to proceed.

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Most of the clients are amazed by this question. They find themselves contemplating where they want to go and they define their goals. (Güner, 2021)

This approach gives important value to the person, the clients feel their worth during the sessions. Everybody comes to the sessions with a story, the therapist listens to the story in an accepting, understanding and constructive manner. However the most important thing he focuses on is the solution and the remedy that may best fit to apply. The therapist does this by basing upon some principles. These principles are; He doesn't change anything that already works. The thing he has been doing, even if it works a little, he goes on doing it. If what he has been doing doesn't work, he doesn't try it again and he passes to something different.

The therapist must love to listen, he must have the desire to witness the process of someone's self-actualization. He should have the capacity to establish a good therapeutic relationship with his client. He has to have love and respect for mankind. He has to know how to follow the non-verbal messages as well, listen well and ask

proper questions. He has to be able to feedback, redefine, dominate the whole process and be ethical. (Güner, 2021)

How to apply Solution-focused Therapy to the clients having eating disorder:

At the first session, therapist asks the client these questions:

- Can you tell me about yourself?
- What do you like to do the most?
- What do you do the best?
- In which areas do you feel successful?
- At the end of the sessions what is it that you desire to reach?

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- Assume that a miracle happens while you're sleeping and when you wake up, you notice that miracle has happened.
- What would be the signs that show you that the miracle has happened. How would you notice the miracle? What else?

Therapists usually use a scale that measures the progress of the problem. At a scale from 0-10, he asks his client to give a number to the course of the problem. 0 means the problem has the client, 10 means the client has progressed and achieved his goal and solved his problem. During every session he asks his client to give a number to the course of the problem. (Güner, 2021)

An example of a session

T: Welcome Ebru, how are you?

E: Fine thanks.

T: Can you tell me a little bit about yourself?

E: I'm 28 years old, a fashion-designer, and live alone in my house.

T: Great! What do you like to do in your spare time?

E: I watch films on TV, meet with friends, go for a walk with my dog.

T: Oh you have a dog, that's nice, you are an animal lover, that's great. So today you've come here, you expect something, you hope something, suppose we have made 5 sessions and at the end of these sessions what is it that you want to achieve?

E: In fact my life is good, I earn money, my designs are liked and my brand is going well, I'm almost a famous fashion designer. However I have some kind of eating disorder. I love to eat,

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and sometimes I exaggerate and eat a lot. Then I'm concerned that I will gain calories and get fat. Now I'm in the middle as you see.

T: You have done a great job by gaining a good reputation at such an early age, And especially recently, it's not easy to earn your own money and live freely and comfortably. You have done it. I congratulate you.

E: Thank you.

T: You say you love to eat and exaggerate eating. So you want to gain control. Then what else do you want to achieve?

E: Because I'm a fashion designer, everybody expects me to be thin and elegant and carry my own dresses well, so they admire me more in this way.

T: Waww you have specified your feelings very well. You have friends and they follow your brand and they also follow you; you want to be a good model for them.

E: That's right. I also want to choose what I eat. I want to eat good food that will be useful for my health and my physical appearance. I don't want to be like a waste basket.

T: In order to achieve this, which of your features will help you?

E: I'm patient, persevering and ambitious. Now you will ask me why I'm here. Why

can't I achieve my goal by myself? Because my fears and my concerns put me in panic and I feel that I will call my concerns towards me and get fat easily.

T: Okay, let's think we have a scale from 0 to 10. 0 is your fears taking you over, 10 is you're taking over your fears. Which number would you give yourself?

E: I think now I'm 3.

T: Okay, if you progress 2 degrees for example, from which signs do you understand this?

E: I think if I become 5, then I find some kind of food that I take pleasure in eating, and at the same time, the calorie of this food should be low, and I could eat it with

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inner calm.

T: Oh you're so creative. That's a very good strategy. Maybe you think about and find more of these strategies until you come to the next session.

E: Yes, why not? When will it be?

T: When do you think you need to come?

E: Next week?

T: Okay, and please make a list of the all positive features about yourself that would help to achieve your goal, before you come to our next session. This is your home-work.

E: I will do that list, I think it will be a long one.

T: I'm sure it will be a long one, bye Ebru,

E: Bye ,,,

In the next session, the therapist asks his client what has gone well during the week. He encourages his client to get relaxed and appreciates his homework and all the good features she has. He always encourages her dreams. He tries to make her see how her life would be after she achieved her goal. He makes her client progress in her dream little by little. He directs her towards her targets by making her visualize her goal. He tries to direct her towards realistic, observable and concrete results that are important for his client. Therapist helps his client to feel productive, self-efficient and self-confident. He also helps his client to apply metaphors, strategies and inspiration sources into her life. Sometimes, the therapist reframes the situation or the problem with different words that would make the client feel better. (Güner, 2021)

Findings

Solution-based therapy can be used for age groups between childhood to the old age. It is used especially to treat depression, anxiety disorders, school problems, relation-ship and family problems and psychiatric disorders. However it is very new that it has been used also for eating and drinking disorders. It can not be used for severe disorders such as; bipolar and schizophrenia. Here in this observation, how solution-based therapy can be used for eating disorders, is investigated and a session

example is given. Eating and drinking disorders are very hard to handle in life, so it is very important if it can be solved as quickly as possible without focusing on the patient's past, just the reverse, it is very practical to focus on the patient's positive and strong sides by giving him hope and making him feel self-sufficient and strong.

Discussion

Eating disorders are much different from going on a diet. Eating disorder affects the patient physiologically, sociologically and psychologically. Diet is trying to establish a good balanced habit of eating in order to reach a healthy position as health and as shape. The patients with eating disorders need the support of clinical psychologists as well as with dieticians.

In order to establish healthy nourishment habits; firstly a person must notice her unhealthy habits and intend to change these habits with the healthy ones. She has to start eating slower. She should eat only if she is hungry. She has to plan her meals and she should pay attention which triggers are affecting his urge to eat. Every habit is a neural circuit. In order to form a new habit one must stimulate this neural circuit so that it can turn out to be automatic. She has to focus on her new healthy and happy life in order to get motivated. She also has to prepare herself a proper ambiance so that; she can only eat healthy food and stay away from the unhealthy ones. (Clear, 2021)

Conclusion

Eating and drinking disorders are cognitive disorders, that shape, weight and the control of these are overvalued. The majority of the patients who have this psychopathology are over involved with their weights and preoccupied with the slightest changes in their weights. These psychopathologies cause some effects on these patients; it may be hard for them to socialize or they may completely evade socialization. The American Psychiatric Association is the union that spearheaded the classification of eating disorders. DSM-IV sorts the disorders as; anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa and not otherwise specified disorders. (NOS). (Fairburn, 2021)

To diagnose anorexia nervosa, the criteria are; to be preoccupied with the shape, weight and the control of these and, evaluate oneself with these and the skill of controlling these. To try to protect a low weight actively even if he or she is already much below the expected weight. To diagnose bulimia nervosa, the criteria are; to overvalue shape, weight and control as in the anorexia nervosa, to lose control and overeat as tucking-in, binge eating and doing this recurrently and sometimes to make herself vomit or use laxatives and diuretics. (NOS :The third group of the serious eating disorders that don't meet the criteria of the first two groups. (Not otherwise specified disorders). This group involves the critical serious criteria that is different from the anorexia nervosa and the bulimia nervosa. (Fairburn, 2021)

Generally eating and drinking disorders are treated by cognitive- behavioral therapy however, if the case is not a severe case, it would be much quicker and easier to treat the disorder by solution-based therapy. Steve De Shazer and Insoo Kim Berg(Güner, 2021) developed goal-directed therapy focusing on the solutions rather than the problems. Solution-focused therapy differs from the conventional therapies by focusing only on the practical sides of the conventional therapies but taking action rapidly and reaching the best solutions. A solution-focused therapist knows that what solves the problem is already potential in the client as his strong and useful features. The therapist listens carefully to the patient, he has the desire to witness the process of someone's self-actualization. He has the capacity to establish a good therapeutic relationship with his client. He knows how to follow the non-verbal messages as well, listen well and ask proper questions. He has to be able to feedback, redefine, dominate the whole process and be ethical. (Güner, 2021)

Limitations

This research is limited to the extent of the data in the world literature. The research is restricted to the research about the related subjects. It is limited to literature surveys.

Notices

Assessment: This study was assessed by internal and external advisors.

Conflicts of Interest: The author declared no conflicts of interest in relation to this article.

Financial Support: The author declared no financial support for the investigation of this research.

Ethical Declaration

This study aims to ensure that scientific research is made in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, respect for the findings and creations of others and aims to realize these principles in the field of related disciplines.

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